

NOTES

Adducts of Copper(II) and Cadmium(II) with Salicylaldehyde Semicarbazone and Monodentate Ligands

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WE report herein the isolation of Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} mixed ligand complexes with salicylaldehyde semicarbazone (hereafter SSCZ) and thiourea (tu)/ γ -picoline (γ -pic)/isoquinoline (iq)/pyridine-*N*-oxide (pyNO) or triphenyl phosphine (Ph_3p) in stoichiometric ratio and their characterisation on the basis of analytical, molecular weight, molar, conductance, magnetic, infrared, electronic and ^1H nmr spectral data.

Experimental

All the chemicals (A.R. grade) were used as such. Salicylaldehyde semicarbazone was prepared as per known method¹.

Preparation of complexes :

$[M(\text{SSCZ})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, where $M = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ or Cd^{II} : Aqueous ethanolic solution of copper chloride/cadmium chloride and acetone-ethanol (1 : 1, v/v) solution of salicylaldehyde semicarbazone were mixed in 1 : 1 molar ratio and ammonia solution was added dropwise till the complexes separated out. The complexes were then filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure.

$[M(\text{SSCZ})L]$, where $M = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ or Cd^{II} and $L = \text{tu}$, γ -pic, iq, pyNO or Ph_3p : Aqueous solutions of copper chloride/cadmium chloride and acetone-ethanol (1 : 1, v/v) solution of salicylaldehyde semicarbazone and ethanolic solutions of tu/ γ -pic/iq/pyNO or Ph_3p were mixed in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The reaction mixture was stirred vigorously and very dilute solution of ammonia was then added dropwise till pH of the solution was ~ 8 . The mixture was digested on a water-bath for 30 min. The resulting solid complexes were washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Copper and cadmium were estimated by pyridine thiocyanate method². Carbon and nitrogen were estimated by a Leco analyser. Ir spectra (KBr) were

recorded using a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (acetone) on a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by Gouy method. The conductance measurements were carried out in $\sim 10^{-3}M$ acetone solution using a Systronic 303 conductivity meter. The molecular weight measurements were carried out by Rast's method using biphenyl as the solvent. The relevant analytical and physical data of the compound are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds were fairly soluble in acetone. The very low values of molar conductance ($1.8 - 3.2 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) indicate that the complexes were non-electrolytes. Molecular weight measurements indicate their monomeric nature. Magnetic moment values for the copper(II) complexes at room temperature were in the normal range (1.70 - 1.84 B.M.).

Deprotonation of phenolic OH and coordination through oxygen of SSCZ was indicated by the occurrence of a band at $1330 - 1350 \text{cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{C}=\text{O}$). A sharp band at $\sim 1600 \text{cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) of the Schiff base indicated the coordination through azomethine nitrogen. Enolisation of the Schiff base in alkaline medium and subsequent coordination to the metal ion through deprotonation of $\text{C}-\text{OH}$ group was indicated by the absence of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ band^{3,4} around 1680cm^{-1} . This was further supported by $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ bands^{3,5,6} appearing at $1230 - 1270 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. An additional band due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ (found by enolisation of the Schiff base) in the alkaline medium at $1470 - 1480 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes confirms the enol coordination of the ligand⁷. The above facts clearly indicate that the ligand salicylaldehyde semicarbazone coordinated as a binegative tridentate (ONO) ligand. The presence of coordinated water molecules in the aquo-complexes was indicated by the bands at 3450 and 830cm^{-1} . However, these bands were absent and new bands were observed in the complexes with monodentate ligands (thiourea, γ -picoline, isoquinoline, pyridine-*N*-oxide or triphenylphosphine). A negative shift of $20 - 25 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ in thiourea complex indicated that thiourea was coordinated through sulphur atom at the metal ion⁸ (685cm^{-1} in free ligand). One of the bands of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}} + \nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ at $\sim 1600 \text{cm}^{-1}$ due to γ -picoline and isoquinoline was found to overlap with the band of salicylaldehyde semicarbazone whereas the other one was found at $\sim 1540 \text{cm}^{-1}$. This suggested the coordination of these ligands through nitrogen atom⁹. The $\nu_{\text{N}=\text{O}}$ band of pyridine-*N*-oxide at 1265cm^{-1} were markedly

TABLE I--ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
			M	N	S/P
[Cu(SSCZ)(H ₂ O)]	Green	215	24.01 (24.57)	16.01 (16.63)	—
[Cu(SSCZ)(tn)]	Leaf green	220	19.75 (20.07)	21.84 (22.11)	9.72 (10.10)
[Cu(SSCZ)(<i>r</i> -pic)]	Light green	230	18.61 (19.40)	16.24 (16.78)	—
[Cu(SSCZ)(iq)]	Parrot green	210	16.74 (17.19)	14.62 (15.15)	—
[Cu(SSCZ)(pyNO)]	Yellowish green	250	18.21 (18.94)	16.32 (16.69)	—
[Cu(SSCZ)(Ph ₃ p)]	Dark green	210	12.03 (12.64)	7.74 (8.36)	7.32 (7.70)
[Cd(SSCZ)(H ₂ O)]	White	210	30.01 (30.56)	13.22 (13.66)	—
[Cd(SSCZ)(tn)]	Yellowish white	215	30.14 (30.76)	18.62 (19.16)	8.32 (8.75)
[Cd(SSCZ)(<i>r</i> -pic)]	Cream white	235	28.84 (29.38)	14.02 (14.64)	—
[Cd(SSCZ)(iq)]	White	220	26.52 (26.86)	12.82 (13.38)	—
[Cd(SSCZ)(pyNO)]	White	235	28.62 (29.24)	14.02 (14.57)	—
[Cd(SSCZ)(Ph ₃ p)]	Pale yellow	230	19.74 (20.38)	7.12 (7.62)	5.12 (5.62)

shifted to 1 210 cm⁻¹ when it is bonded to metal through oxygen atom. This shifting to lower frequency could be attributed to change in the N—O bond order as a result of coordination of the ligand through its oxygen atom^{10,11}. In the triphenylphosphine complex strong and sharp bands were observed at 1 480, 1 440 and 1 095 cm⁻¹ due to coordinated ligand of the complexes¹². Some new bands which appeared around 520–510 and 420–410 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra of the complexes were due to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} respectively^{13,14}.

Nmr spectra: ¹H nmr spectrum (DMSO-d₆) of the ligand SSCZ showed characteristic signals at δ 8.48 for CH=N proton, 7.82 for NH proton and around 5.85 for phenolic proton. In the spectrum of [Cu(SSCZ)H₂O] the signal due to CH=N proton showed downfield shift to δ 8.8 indicating coordination through azomethine nitrogen. The disappearance of signals due to NH proton suggested¹⁵ the removal of this proton via enolization. Further, the disappearance of signals due to phenolic proton, NH protons indicated dinegative (OON) tridentate chelation by the ligand.

The electronic spectra of the copper(II) complexes showed three bands at 15 500, 19 500 and 22 000 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ²B_{1g}→³A_{1g}, ²B_{1g}→²E_g transitions and charge transfer respectively, which indicated square-planar stereochemistry for copper(II)¹⁶.

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Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) Complexes of *N*-Phenyl-*N'*-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl Thiocarbamide

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WE describe herein the synthesis of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes with *N*-phenyl-*N'*-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl thiocarbamide (1), and their charac-